

On N_m -semi-open sets in neutrosophic minimal structure spaces

S. Ganesan^{1*}, S. Jafari², F. Smarandache³ and R. Karthikeyan⁴

¹ Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Mathematics,

Raja Doraisingam Government Arts College, Sivagangai-630561, Tamil Nadu, India.

(Affiliated to Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu, India). ORCID iD: [0000-0002-7728-8941](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7728-8941)

² College of Vestsjaelland South & Mathematical and Physical Science Foundation,
4200 Slagelse, Denmark.

ORCID iD: [0000-0001-5744-7354](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5744-7354)

³ Mathematics & Science Department, University of New Maxico, 705 Gurley Ave,
Gallup, NM 87301, USA. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-5560-5926](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5560-5926)

⁴ Scholar, PG & Research Department of Mathematics,

Raja Doraisingam Government Arts College, Sivagangai-630561, Tamil Nadu, India.

(Affiliated to Alagappa University, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu, India). ORCID iD: [0000-0001-5277-5201](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5277-5201)

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Abstract: The focuses of this article, we study the notions of N_m -semi-open sets, N_m -semi-interior, N_m -semi-closure, N_m -semi-continuous maps in neutrosophic minimal structures & some basic concepts.

Key words: Neutrosophic minimal structure spaces (in short, nms), N_m -semi-closed, N_m -semi-open and N_m -semi-continuous

1. Introduction

L. A. Zadeh's [16] Fuzzy set concepts laid the foundation of many theories such as neutrosophic sets, soft sets, etc. K. T. Atanassov's [4] intuitionistic fuzzy set theory in many areas such as topology, computer science and so on. F. Smarandache [14, 15] found that some objects have indeterminacy or neutral other than membership and non-membership. A. A. Salama & S. A. Alblowi[13], introduced and studied some fundamental properties of neutrosophic set (in short., ns) & neutrosophic topological spaces (in short., nt). V. Popa & T. Noiri [12] introduced the notions of of minimal structure spaces. M. Karthika et al [11] introduced and studied nms. (ie., N_m -closed, N_m -open, N_m -closure, N_m -interior, union property, intersection property , N_m - maps and so on,...). We analysis of N_m -semi-closed sets, N_m -semi-open sets, N_m -semi-closure and N_m -semi-interior operators in nms. Finally, we introduce N_m -semi-continuous map and investigate some properties of such concepts.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [13] A nt in Salama's sense on a nonempty set X is a family τ of ns in X satisfying three axioms:

1. Empty set (0_\sim) and universal set(1_\sim) are members of τ .
2. $K_1 \cap K_2 \in \tau$ where $K_1, K_2 \in \tau$.

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*Correspondence: sgsgsgsg77@gmail.com

3. $\cup K_\delta \in \tau$ for every $\{K_\delta : \delta \in \Delta\} \leq \tau$.

Definition 2.2. [11] Let nms over a universal set Ω be denoted by N_m . N_m is said to be nms over Ω if it satisfies following the axiom: $0_\sim, 1_\sim \in N_m$. A family of nms is denoted by $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$.

3. N_m -semi-open

Definition 3.1. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms. A subset W of Ω is said to be N_m -semi-open set (in short, N_m -sos) if $W \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(W))$. The complement of an N_m -sos is called an N_m -scs.

Remark 3.1. Let (Ω, \mathcal{T}) be a nt & $W \leq \Omega$. W is called an N_m -semi-open set (in short, N_m -sos) [10] if $W \leq \mathcal{N} \text{cl}(\mathcal{N} \text{int}(W))$. If the nms $N_{m\Omega}$ is a topology, clearly an N_m -sos is N_m -sos.

Lemma 3.1. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms. Then

1. Every N_m sos is N_m -sos.
2. W is an N_m -sos iff $W \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(W))$.
3. Every N_m -cs is N_m -scs.
4. W is an N_m -scs iff $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(W)) \leq W$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms. The arbitrary union of N_m -sos is a N_m -sos.

Proof. Let W_δ be an N_m -sos for $\delta \in \Delta$. From Definition 3.1 and Proposition 3.8 (vi) [11], it follows $W_\delta \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(W_\delta)) \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(\cup W_\delta))$. This implies $\cup W_\delta \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(\cup W_\delta))$. Hence $\cup W_\delta$ is an N_m -sos. \square

Remark 3.2. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms. The intersection of any two N_m -sos may not be N_m -sos.

Example 3.1. Let $\Omega = \{\omega\}$ with $N_m = \{0_\sim, P_1, Q_1, R_1, S_1, 1_\sim\}$ and $N_m^C = \{1_\sim, I_1, J_1, K_1, L_1, 0_\sim\}$ where

$P_1 = \prec (1, 0.5, 0.6) \succ$; $Q_1 = \prec (0, 0.9, 0.2) \succ$; $R_1 = \prec (1, 0.9, 0.2) \succ$; $S_1 = \prec (0.8, 0.5, 0.6) \succ$

$I_1 = \prec (0.6, 0.5, 1) \succ$; $J_1 = \prec (0.2, 0.1, 0) \succ$; $K_1 = \prec (0.2, 0.1, 1) \succ$; $L_1 = \prec (0.6, 0.5, 0) \succ$

Now we define the two N_m -sos as follows:

$A = \prec (1, 0.5, 0.6) \succ$; $B = \prec (0.8, 0.5, 0.2) \succ$

Here $N_m \text{int}(A) = P_1$, $N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(A)) = N_m \text{cl}(P_1) = 0_\sim^C$ and

$N_m \text{int}(B) = S_1$, $N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(B)) = N_m \text{cl}(S_1) = 0_\sim^C$. But $A \wedge B = \prec (0.8, 0.5, 0.6) \succ$ is not a N_m -sos in Ω .

Definition 3.2. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms. For a subset W of Ω . Then,

1. N_m -semi-closure of $W = \min \{I : I \text{ is } N_m \text{-scs and } I \geq W\}$, it is denoted by $N_m \text{-scl}(W)$.
2. N_m -semi-interior of $W = \max \{G : G \text{ is } N_m \text{-sos and } G \leq W\}$, it is denoted by $N_m \text{-sint}(W)$.

Theorem 3.2. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms and $W \leq \Omega$. Then

1. $N_m\text{-sint}(W) \leq W$.
2. If $W \leq Z$, then $N_m\text{-sint}(W) \leq N_m\text{-sint}(Z)$.
3. W is $N_m\text{-sos}$ iff $N_m\text{-sint}(W) = W$.
4. $N_m\text{-sint}(N_m\text{-sint}(W)) = N_m\text{-sint}(W)$.
5. $N_m\text{-scl}(\Omega - W) = \Omega - N_m\text{-sint}(W)$ and $N_m\text{-sint}(\Omega - W) = \Omega - N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.

Proof. (1), (2) Obvious.

(3) by theorem 3.1.

(4) by (3).

(5) $W \leq \Omega, \Omega - N_m\text{-sint}(W) = \Omega - \max\{U : U \leq W, U \text{ is } N_m\text{-sos}\} = \min\{\Omega - U : U \leq W, U \text{ is } N_m\text{-sos}\} = \min\{\Omega - U : \Omega - W \leq \Omega - U, U \text{ is } N_m\text{-sos}\} = N_m\text{-scl}(\Omega - W)$.

Similarly, we have $N_m\text{-sint}(\Omega - W) = \Omega - N_m\text{-scl}(W)$. □

Theorem 3.3. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms and $W \leq \Omega$. Then

1. $W \leq N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.
2. If $W \leq Z$, then $N_m\text{-scl}(W) \leq N_m\text{-scl}(Z)$.
3. F is $N_m\text{-scs}$ iff $N_m\text{-scl}(F) = F$.
4. $N_m\text{-scl}(N_m\text{-scl}(W)) = N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.

Proof. Similar to by theorem 3.2. □

Theorem 3.4. Let $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms & $W \leq \Omega$. Then

1. $\omega \in N_m\text{-scl}(W)$ iff if $W \cap M \neq \emptyset$ for every $N_m\text{-sos}$ M containing ω .
2. $\omega \in N_m\text{-sint}(W)$ iff there exists an $N_m\text{-sos}$ K such that $K \leq W$.

Proof. (1) \exists there is an $N_m\text{-sos}$ M containing ω such that $W \cap M = \emptyset$. $\Omega - M$ is an $N_m\text{-scs}$ such that $W \leq \Omega - M$, $\omega \notin \Omega - M$. This implies $\omega \notin N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.

The reverse relation is true.

(2) Obvious. □

Lemma 3.2. $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ be a nms & $W \leq \Omega$.

1. $N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(W)) \leq N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{-scl}(W))) \leq N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.
2. $N_m\text{-sint}(W) \leq N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{-sint}(W))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{int}(W))$.

Proof. (1) For $W \leq \Omega$, by Theorem 3.3, $N_m\text{-scl}(W)$ is an $N_m\text{-scs}$. Hence from Lemma 3.1, we have $N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(W)) \leq N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{-scl}(W))) \leq N_m\text{-scl}(W)$.

(2) similar by the proof of (1). □

Definition 3.3. Let $l : (\Omega, N_{m\Omega}) \rightarrow (\Lambda, N_{m\Lambda})$ is called N_m -semi-continuous map (in short, N_m -sc) iff $l^{-1}(V) \in N_m$ -sos whenever $V \in N_{m\Lambda}$.

Theorem 3.5. Every neutrosophic minimal continuous is N_m -sc but not conversely.

Proof. By Lemma 3.1 (1). □

Theorem 3.6. Let $l : \Omega \rightarrow \Lambda$ be a map on two nms $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ and $(\Lambda, N_{m\Lambda})$.

1. l is N_m -sc.
2. $l^{-1}(M)$ is an N_m -sos for each N_m os M in Λ .
3. $l^{-1}(Z)$ is an N_m -scs for each N_m -cs Z in Λ .
4. $l(N_m\text{-scl}(W)) \leq N_m\text{cl}(l(W))$ for $W \leq \Omega$.
5. $N_m\text{-scl}(l^{-1}(Z)) \leq l^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(Z))$ for $Z \leq \Lambda$.
6. $l^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(Z)) \leq N_m\text{-sint}(l^{-1}(Z))$ for $Z \leq \Lambda$.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let M be an N_m os in Λ & $\omega \in l^{-1}(M)$. By hypothesis, there exists an N_m -sos U_ω containing ω such that $l(U) \leq M$. This implies $\omega \in U_\omega \leq l^{-1}(M)$ for all $\omega \in l^{-1}(M)$. Hence by Theorem 3.1, $l^{-1}(M)$ is N_m -sos.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Obvious.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) For $W \leq \Omega$, $l^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(l(W))) = l^{-1}(\min \{S \leq \Lambda : l(W) \leq S \text{ and } S \text{ is } N_m\text{-closed}\}) = \min \{l^{-1}(S) \leq \Omega : W \leq l^{-1}(S) \text{ and } S \text{ is } N_m\text{-scs}\} \geq \min \{R \leq \Omega : W \leq R \text{ and } R \text{ is } N_m\text{-scs}\} = N_m\text{-scl}(W)$. Hence $l(N_m\text{-scl}(W)) \leq N_m\text{cl}(l(W))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) For $W \leq \Omega$, from (4), it follows $l(N_m\text{-scl}(l^{-1}(W))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(l(l^{-1}(W))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(W)$. Hence we get (5).

(5) \Rightarrow (6) For $Z \leq \Lambda$, from $N_m\text{int}(Z) = \Lambda - N_m\text{cl}(\Lambda - Z)$ and (5), it follows: $l^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(Z)) = l^{-1}(\Lambda - N_m\text{cl}(\Lambda - Z)) = \Omega - l^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(\Lambda - Z)) \leq \Omega - N_m\text{-scl}(l^{-1}(\Lambda - Z)) = N_m\text{-sint}(l^{-1}(Z))$. Hence (6) is obtained.

(6) \Rightarrow (1) Let $\omega \in \Omega$ and M an N_m os containing $l(\omega)$. From (6) & Proposition 3.8 [11], it follows $\omega \in l^{-1}(M) = l^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(M)) \leq N_m\text{-sint}(l^{-1}(M))$. Theorem 3.4, \exists N_m -sos U containing ω such that $\omega \in U \leq l^{-1}(M)$. Hence l is N_m -sc. □

Theorem 3.7. $l : \Omega \rightarrow \Lambda$ be a map on two nms $(\Omega, N_{m\Omega})$ and $(\Lambda, N_{m\Lambda})$.

1. l is N_m -sc.
2. $l^{-1}(M) \leq N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{int}(l^{-1}(M)))$ for each N_m os M in Λ .
3. $N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(l^{-1}(R))) \leq l^{-1}(R)$ for each N_m -cs R in Λ .
4. $l(N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(W))) \leq N_m\text{cl}(l(W))$ for $W \leq \Omega$.
5. $N_m\text{int}(N_m\text{cl}(l^{-1}(Z))) \leq l^{-1}(N_m\text{cl}(Z))$ for $Z \leq \Lambda$.
6. $l^{-1}(N_m\text{int}(Z)) \leq N_m\text{cl}(N_m\text{int}(l^{-1}(Z)))$ for $Z \leq \Lambda$.

Proof. (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) By theorem 3.6 and definition of N_m -sos.

(1) \Leftrightarrow (3) By theorem 3.6 and lemma 3.1.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) Let $W \leq \Omega$. Then from Theorem 3.6(4) and Lemma 3.2, it follows $N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(W)) \leq N_m \text{-scl}(W) \leq l^{-1}(N_m \text{cl}(l(W)))$. Hence $l(N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(W))) \leq N_m \text{cl}(l(W))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) Obvious.

(5) \Rightarrow (6) From (5) and Proposition 3.8 [11], it follows: $l^{-1}(N_m \text{int}(Z)) = l^{-1}(\Lambda - N_m \text{cl}(\Lambda - Z)) = \Omega - l^{-1}(N_m \text{cl}(\Lambda - Z)) \leq \Omega - N_m \text{int}(N_m \text{cl}(l^{-1}(\Lambda - Z))) = N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(l^{-1}(Z)))$. Hence, (6) is obtained.

(6) \Rightarrow (1) Let M be an N_m os in Λ . Then by (6) and Proposition 3.8 [11], we have $l^{-1}(M) = l^{-1}(N_m \text{int}(M)) \leq N_m \text{cl}(N_m \text{int}(l^{-1}(M)))$. This implies $l^{-1}(M)$ is an N_m -sos. Hence by (2), l is N_m -semi-continuous. \square

Conclusion

We presented several new notions and related properties by utilizing the concept of N_m -sos in nms.

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